

New *meso*-substituted Porphyrins bearing Heterocyclic Bases. Magnetic Resonance and Electrochemical Studies

P. SURIYANARAYANAN and V. KRISHNAN*

Department of Inorganic and Physical Chemistry, Indian Institute of Science, Bangalore-560 013

The preparation of porphyrins appended with heterocyclic bases, pyrazole, quinoline and indole is described. The free-base porphyrins either fully or partially substituted in the *meso* positions are characterised by ^1H nmr spectral method. The existence of atropisomers is demonstrated in tetrakis pyrazolyl porphyrin. The electrochemical data of the free-base porphyrins reveal the influence of electron donating and electron withdrawing substituents on the porphyrin ring redox potentials.

INCREASING attention has been paid towards the synthesis of *meso*-substituted porphyrins owing to their importance in pharmaceutical applications¹ and other physicochemical properties². The presence of different substituents in the *meso* positions, viz. pyridine³, furan⁴ and quinoline⁵ are known to alter significantly the structural and electrochemical redox properties. Moreover, the presence of bulky substituents in the *meso* positions of the porphyrins permits the existence of range of stereoisomers with different properties. Further, covalent attachment of heterocyclic bases to the porphyrins provide additional metal chelation sites and thus would be of interest to study metal-metal interactions within a molecular system. The present work was undertaken with a view to prepare sterically crowded porphyrins bearing bulky heterocyclic groups in the *meso* positions and to investigate the dependence of structural features on the physicochemical properties.

We report here the synthesis of new porphyrins bearing substituted pyrazolyl, quinolyl and indole groups appended either partially or fully in the *meso* positions of the porphyrins. In an earlier report⁶, we described the intra-molecular charge-transfer resonance in a few heterocyclic appended porphyrins. Here, we present evidence for the existence of atropisomerism in these porphyrins from ^1H nmr study. The cyclic voltammetry studies on the free-base porphyrins are used to arrive at the influence of the relative basicities of the heterocyclic groups on the ring oxidation-reduction potentials of the porphyrins.

Experimental

All starting materials used were of analytical grade. The solvents employed in the study were distilled prior to use. The ^1H nmr spectra were recorded on a Bruker WH 270 MHz FT NMR spectrometer using CDCl_3 as solvent and TMS as an internal standard. All the spectra were recorded at ambient temperature. Cyclic voltammetry

measurements were carried out using a three electrode potentiostatic circuit and a MPI 1042 voltammetry controller in conjunction with MFE platomatic 715 M X-Y recorder. The working electrode was a platinum button electrode. A platinum wire was used as a counter electrode. The voltammograms of the free-base porphyrins were measured in CH_2Cl_2 solution ($\sim 10^{-5}$ M) using tetrabutyl ammonium perchlorate as a base electrolyte. The potentials are with reference to SCE.

The synthesis of porphyrins was accomplished according to Scheme 1 using the method of Adler *et al.*⁷. The formylated heterocycles, 1,3-diphenyl pyrazole-4-carboxaldehyde⁸, 2-chloro-7-methyl-3-formylquinoline⁹ and 3-formylindole¹⁰ have been prepared according to the methods described in literature. A typical procedure for the synthesis of 5,10,15,20-tetrakis[4-(1,3-diphenyl)pyrazolyl]porphyrin is outlined here.

Freshly distilled pyrrole (7.20 ml, 0.105 mol) was added to a refluxing propionic acid (500 ml) containing 1,3-diphenyl-4-formylpyrazole (24.8 g, 0.1 mol). The mixture was refluxed for 30 min and left overnight. The propionic acid was removed from the reaction mixture under vacuum and the residue washed with 10% aqueous ammonia solution followed by methanol. The crude product obtained was then dissolved in CHCl_3 (5.0 ml) and chromatographed on a basic alumina column. The chlorine and the acid impurities remained in the column and the product was eluted with CHCl_3 . After evaporation of the solvent, the product was taken in benzene and chromatographed on silica gel to get partially purified product. In order to obtain the pure tetrasubstituted porphyrin, the product was dissolved in a solvent mixture, heptane-benzene (1 : 1, v/v), and subjected to tlc on silica gel. Four closely-spaced bands, arising from different atropisomers, were observed. It was found difficult to separate these fractions from each other. Similar procedures were adopted for the synthesis of other porphyrins. The partially substituted

Scheme 1. Condensation reaction of pyrrole with heterocyclic aldehydes.

porphyrins are obtained by using appropriate ratios of the reactants (Scheme 1).

Results and Discussion

The structures of the synthesised porphyrins are shown below.

The disubstituted porphyrins can exist in *cis* or *trans* isomer, however, owing to the close R_f values, it was found difficult to separate these isomers. The optical absorption and emission features of these porphyrins have been described⁶ earlier. The results of the 1H nmr studies are presented here.

The 1H nmr spectra of the free-base porphyrins (Fig. 1) are highly characteristic and all the proton resonances have been assigned based on integrated intensities. The appearance of β -pyrrole (δ 8.80) and the inner imino protons (δ -2.60) in the spectra confirm the existence of porphyrinic core. The singlet resonance of the imino (NH) protons in these porphyrins implies that the inner NH groups are in *trans* configuration¹¹. Interestingly, the position of this resonance is found to vary with the nature of the substituent as TPZ (δ -2.48) < TIP (-2.61) $\sim$ TQP (-2.69). A similar behaviour is observed for the β -pyrrole proton resonances. Thus, the β -pyrrole proton resonance of the different substituted porphyrins occur at δ 8.04, 8.83 and 8.93 respectively for TPZ, TIP and TQP. These two observations indicate that the nature of the heterocyclic substituent alters the electron densities at the β -pyrrole carbons. The occurrence of β -pyrrole proton resonance of TPZ in the down-field region relative to that observed for other porphyrins is ascribed to electron donating ability of pyrazole moiety. Such effects have been observed earlier in porphyrins¹². It is interesting to note that the β -pyrrole protons resonate as a complex multiplet in the partially (tris, bis and mono) substituted porphyrins (Fig. 2). The complexity of the multiplet arises from the unsymmetrical distribution of the substituents. The structure of these multiplets exhibits a mirror image relationship indicating the complementarity of the *meso* substituents¹².

We shall now consider the proton resonances of the heterocycle part. A comparison of the 1H nmr

Fig. 1. ^1H nmr spectra of (a) TPZ, (b) TQP and (c) TIP in CDCl_3 ; (x) resonances due to impurities/solvents.

spectra of the respective heterocyclic aldehydes with those obtained for substituted porphyrins reveals that the proton resonances of the appended groups are shifted both upfield and downfield relative to the resonances of free-aldehyde group. The magnitudes of the shifts are, however, critically dependent on the proximity of the proton to the porphyrin nucleus indicating the influence of porphyrin ring

anisotropy effect on the proton resonances. It is seen that the singlet resonance at δ 8.55 arising from the proton-5 of the 1,3-diphenylpyrazolyl-4-aldehyde appears as a complex multiplet centered at δ 8.96 in TPZ. It is of interest to note that the *ortho*-proton resonance of the N-phenyl and C-phenyl groups occur in the downfield region in TPZ relative to the free aldehyde. The observation of 5, 4

Fig. 2. ^1H nmr spectra of partially substituted quinolylporphyrins: (a) MQP, (b) BQP and (c) Tris QP in CDCl_3 ; (x) resonances due to impurities/solvents.

and 2-proton resonances respectively of TPZ, TQP and TIP in the deshielded region is analogous to the *ortho*-proton resonances of the *meso*-aryl group of the tetraphenylporphyrin (TPP)¹⁴.

The presence of bulky heterocyclic substituent in the *meso* positions of the porphyrins should lead to the existence of atropisomers^{15,16}. Owing to the steric feature, it can be reckoned that the protons nearer to the porphyrin can either come under the influence of the π -current or lie outside of it. It is known that when the protons experience the π -current effect, its resonance is shifted upfield relative to the unaffected proton resonance while a downfield shift in the proton resonance is expected when the protons lie outside the perimeter of the π -current effect. It is clearly seen in the ^1H nmr spectra of TPZ that the 5-proton resonance occurs in the downfield region as a complex multiplet indicating that the C-aryl group is possibly located inside the perimeter of the π -ring current effect. The relative intensities of the resonance lines in the complex multiplet are analysed to identify the nature of the atropisomer. It is found difficult to arrive at the statistical distribution of the atropisomers in the TPZ. It can be surmised that the isolated TPZ is possibly a mixture of atropisomers. This is also

revealed from the closeness of bands in the tlc plate during the purification process of TPZ.

The cyclic voltammograms of representative pyrazolylporphyrins are shown in Fig. 3. The ring oxidation and reduction potentials represented here corresponds to one-electron transfer and these are calculated as the average of cathodic and anodic peaks. The potentials of the heterocyclic appended porphyrins are compared with those observed for TPP in Table 1. The difference between the first ring oxidation potential and first ring reduction potential of these porphyrins lie in a range (2.10 to 2.20 eV) similar to that observed for TPP¹⁷. However, it is noteworthy that the magnitudes of these potentials are different from that of TPP. The first ring oxidation potential of the tetrakis-substituted porphyrins occur at less anodic potentials relative to that of TPP indicating the effect of the heterocyclic substituent in the π -electron manifold of the porphyrins. This effect is less pronounced in the mono-substituted porphyrins. It is known¹⁸ that the difference between the first and second reduction potentials, Δ , ($E_{1/2}^{\text{I}}$ - $E_{1/2}^{\text{II}}$), bears a relationship with the nature of the substituent group (σ values of the substituent). Momenteau *et al.*⁴ compared the value of Δ for the furan appended porphyrin

Fig. 3. Cyclic voltammograms of (1) TPZ and (2) MPZ in CH_2Cl_2 ; concn. of porphyrins 1 mM in presence of 0.1 M TBAP as supporting electrolyte; (a) oxidation and (b) reduction parts. Potentials of TPZ are with reference to Ag/AgCl while that of MPZ are to SCE.

TABLE 1—RING OXIDATION-REDUCTION-POTENTIALS (V) OF FREE-BASE HETEROCYCLE APPENDED PORPHYRINS IN CH_2Cl_2 AT 25°C^a

Porphyrin	Oxidation potentials		Reduction potentials	
	$E_{1/2}^I$	$E_{1/2}^{II}$	$E_{1/2}^I$	$E_{1/2}^{II}$
TPZ	0.97	1.33	-1.09	-1.37
TQP	0.87	1.39	^b	-1.35
MtZ	1.05	1.49	-1.22	-1.60
MQP	1.05	1.52	-1.25	-1.70
MIP	1.14	1.46	-1.37	-1.60
TPP	1.00	1.13	-1.08	-1.50

^a Potential reported are with respect to SCE. ^b Not observed.

with TPP and suggested that a higher Δ value signifies the electron-withdrawing nature of the substituent. In the present study, the Δ values are found to be 0.38, 0.45 and 0.49 eV respectively for

MPZ, MQP and MIP. The Δ value observed for MIP deserves special mention since this value is 0.11 unit greater than that observed for TPP (0.42), signifying the electron-withdrawing nature of the substituent. It can be further seen that the first ring reductions of MPZ and MQP occur at more cathodic potential relative to TPP, indicating the basic nature of these porphyrins.

From the foregoing discussions, it is seen that the heterocyclic substituents in the *meso* positions modify the physicochemical properties to a large extent. These new substituted porphyrins will permit an extensive comparative investigation of the metal derivatives.

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